

Use of Simulation for Chemotherapy Competency Training

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Background

- Chemotherapy identified as a hazardous drug
- Chemotherapy administration certification originally included hands-on practice. It is now done using online self-learning module
- Simulation has been found to be an effective teaching strategy for nurses to hone their clinical skills

Problem

- An increase in chemotherapy medication errors was noted at this project facility, tied to newly certified nurses
- Newly certified verbally reported a lack of confidence and competency when administering chemotherapy

Purpose

To assess if confidence and competence levels during chemotherapy administration would increase among new oncology nurses, if simulation training was provided

Three Step Model (Lewin, 1947)

- 1) UNFREEZE: Collect chemotherapy administration error data; obtain facility support for project; create oncology leadership committee; inform new oncology nurses about simulation training sessions
- 2) CHANGE: Provide a 4-hour chemotherapy administration simulation course
- 3) REFREEZE: Review facility's policy on chemotherapy certification to determine if simulation training should be required

Methods

Design/Setting: Quality improvement project in a Los Angeles community facility's simulation center

Participants: Eleven inpatient oncology unit nurses who were chemotherapy certified during 2020

Measures:

- Self-Confidence survey from the *NLN Student Satisfaction and Self-Confidence in Learning Scale*
- Facility's *Chemotherapy/Immunotherapy Administration Competency Verification Form*

Procedures:

- 1) Self-Confidence Survey pre-simulation
- 2) Simulation 1 – competency score
- 3) Debriefing using GAS Framework
- 4) Simulation 2 – competency score
- 5) Debriefing using GAS Framework
- 6) Self-Confidence Survey post-simulation

Results

Key Findings

- All nurses improved their self-confidence and competency scores after completing two chemotherapy simulations and both debriefing sessions
- Mean improvement competency score for all participants was 4.7
- The largest improvement in competency score was for Nurse 3 (up to 12 points after simulation session 2)
- Participants were engaged learners during both debriefing sessions
- Relationship between competence and self-confidence score was inconclusive

Limitations

- Had a small sample size of 11 nurses
- Some technical issues occurred with the facility's high-fidelity manikin
- COVID-19 social distancing procedures during debriefing sessions made it more difficult for participants to hear everything

Conclusions

- Simulations for chemotherapy administration has the ability to enhance skills & self-confidence in newly certified oncology nurses
- Factors to consider include simulation equipment/staff, space & other costs
- This is a PI project that may easily be replicated, as well as one that could result in decreasing the number of chemotherapy administration errors